

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND PROPOSALS FOR IMPROVING TRANSPORT SERVICES IN THE CITY OF SAMARKAND

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Abstract. In Samarkand region, road transport holds the largest share among all transportation services, accounting for more than 51% of the total. Especially in the urban area, there is significant potential to expand this type of service. This article builds upon the results and recommendations of our previous research, aiming to offer practical suggestions to relevant system implementers. The problems identified and their proposed solutions are closely aligned with ongoing reforms in the country's transportation sector. Particular attention is given to the presentation held on April 29, 2025, during the President's visit to Samarkand, where strategic plans for the development of the city's transport system were discussed. One of the key objectives of these plans is to transform Samarkand into a city with a population exceeding one million. The article also examines similar shortcomings observed in Tashkent's transport system, offering comparative analysis and recommendations applicable to Samarkand.

Keywords: transport services, strategy, over one million, growth rate, regional research, Development Bank, congestion map.

INTRODUCTION.

The main focus of this article is to improve the passenger transportation service in the city of Samarkand, propose additions to existing routes, suggest new service types by introducing new routes, and thereby increase the system's revenue share. Additionally, it aims to incorporate elements of digitalization into the system's structure and management [7]. In the region, including the city, among all types of services, automobile transport services hold the largest share, accounting for more than 51% of total services. To clarify this data further, we attempted to study the current year's statistics based on available data. According to recent information, during January–August 2024, the total volume of transport services in Samarkand region amounted to 4,888.3 billion UZS, with automobile transport services having a dominant share of 89.3%. The data is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dynamics of transport service provision in Samarkand region from January to August 2024.

It is evident that the volume of transport services in the city of Samarkand has significantly increased in recent years and continues to grow. Below is a table presenting the indicators for the initial periods of 2023 and 2024 based on the available statistical data:

Table 1

Volume of transport services in the city of Samarkand

Period	Volume (billion UZS)	Growth rate (%)	Note
January–November 2023	6,123.2	109.2	Total volume of transport services.
January–August 2024	4,888.3	122.0	Total volume of transport services.

To further develop these indicators, construction of new types of roads has been planned from this year. One such project is the Tashkent–Samarkand toll highway. In 2025, it is planned to begin the construction of a six-lane toll highway with a total length of 300 km. The construction is expected to be completed by the end of 2028. The project is intended to be implemented based on a public-private partnership.

METHODOLOGY.

For these roads, the purchase of electric buses began during 2023–2025 for the Samarkand city public transportation system, along with the procurement of charging equipment. The project is being carried out with the participation of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD). With the launch of this project, the revenue in the system is expected to increase even further. Thus, in 2025–2026, the city of Samarkand is expected to implement large-scale reforms aimed at modernizing the public transportation system and ensuring environmental cleanliness.

The city of Samarkand has signed a contract with the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) for the purchase of 350 electric buses. Within this framework, 100 buses were delivered by the end of 2023, and the rest are expected to arrive by 2025. This project is supported by a fund of 95 million USD.

According to the system plan, it is intended to open 40 new bus routes in the city of Samarkand, of which 5 will be express routes serving to connect the airport, railway station, and historical center. In order to further improve and automate the innovations in the system, it is planned to fully digitize the transport system. Currently, an electronic ticket payment system has been introduced in the Samarkand transport system, through which passengers have begun to use an automated method for making payments.

As we know, one of the goals outlined in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 is to rapidly develop the national economy and ensure high growth rates, including increasing the volume of the regional economy by 1.4–1.6 times. According to the data, transport services rank second (22.7%) among market services by type of economic activity, after trade services. The second goal of this article is the issue of traffic congestion. Regarding this matter, indicators observed in the city of Tashkent studied by the aforementioned institute are shown in the following map:

Figure 2. Studying the Environmental Situation in Tashkent City

In this figure, green dots represent university buildings. Based on the traffic congestion map, roads with vehicle speeds below 10 km/h are shown in dark red, those with speeds between 10–25 km/h in red, 25–45 km/h in yellow, and over 45 km/h in green. Taking this into account, only red and dark red roads were analyzed.

The study found that the total length of highly congested roads in Tashkent currently exceeds 120 km — longer than the distance from Tashkent to Gulistan (119 km). 43% of all higher education institutions in the country are located in Tashkent, and 34% of all students (354,000) study in the capital. 47% of survey participants identified student commuting as one of the top three causes of traffic congestion. Additionally, 78% of students rated congestion as one of the main problems. Among surveyed students, 9.3% said they engage in gig work during their free time, and 91% of these are students who came to Tashkent from other regions. This indicates that many are forced to work part-time to cover their daily expenses, which negatively affects the quality of their education.

Increased student activity during the academic period leads to the length of extremely congested roads rising from 8.5 km to 11.3 km. Due to increased congestion during the academic year, an additional 507 tons of CO₂ is emitted into the atmosphere annually. To offset this, approximately 19,031 trees would need to be planted or 53 hectares of green space established. It is important to note that the centralization of higher education institutions in the capital forces many young people from other regions to relocate to Tashkent for education. The relatively high cost of living, lack of student housing, and expensive rent in the city significantly increase the cost of education.

Locating educational institutions that train specialists for specific sectors of the economy in regions where those sectors are concentrated would help integrate science, education, and industry, thereby improving the quality of education. Moreover, the increase in service facilities

around universities can have a multiplicative effect on local economic development and help reduce interregional disparities.

To prevent the replication of Tashkent's traffic congestion in Samarkand, it is proposed to organize quality and convenient public transport services from district centers to the city center. Passengers would be encouraged to leave their personal vehicles at parking lots on the outskirts and use public transportation instead. This would involve developing modernized roads from the outskirts to the center, with low traffic congestion and clearly scheduled services.

Initial solutions to these problems have already begun to be implemented in system projects. One such measure is the creation of bus lanes on most city roads, which lays the groundwork for solving the issue. Most people coming from outside the city visit government offices, medical centers, educational and cultural institutions, recreational areas, and playgrounds for adults and children.

However, the parking facilities around these institutions are insufficient to accommodate incoming vehicles, causing significant inconvenience for visitors. Thus, providing quality services for these groups would encourage them to use public transportation.

Another method of encouraging public transport usage is offering discounted tickets. For example, discounts could be provided to school students, university students, retirees, and individuals with disabilities. Additional efforts could include introducing sightseeing services on buses, announcing stops close to popular destinations, and most importantly, launching express routes.

Another proposed solution is to bring currently semi-regulated transportation services that operate between city outskirts, district centers, and residential areas under the city's public transport management. If implemented, direct routes could be established from outer-city parking lots to major destinations like medical centers and health resorts. Vehicles could also display route information clearly to inform passengers of their destinations and nearby stops. This would not only bring order to the city's transport system but also significantly increase revenue.

On April 29 of this year, during a presentation on the development of Samarkand's transport system, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev mentioned that under Uzbekistan's Development Strategy, Samarkand is planned to become a city with over one million residents. As part of this plan, new districts like "Qorasuv" will be built on the city's outskirts. He also shared the following information about daily visitors to Samarkand:

"Currently, considering both permanent residents and visitors from other districts, 925,000 people move around Samarkand's roads daily. Of these, 592,000 use personal vehicles, while more than 330,000 use public transport." This imbalance is explained by the lack of convenient and reliable public transport. Transport providers tend to operate during peak hours rather than throughout the day. Over the past two years, 38 routes were discontinued due to unprofitability, and there is a shortage of 300 buses.

Although this article is a modest attempt to address these problems, it could positively contribute to optimizing the system's income, reducing harmful gas emissions from vehicles, and preserving the environment. As part of the article's analysis of ecological damage caused by urban transport and to promote the idea of providing discounted tickets for university students, a survey was conducted among 162 students of TDIU Samarkand Branch. The results showed that 80% of students expressed a desire for the availability of discounted tickets.

Compilation	Email	Name	How long do you use public transport	are you happy	is it important	What is important	How much discount	Discou	In what transport mode	If applicable, what type of ticket	Your residence	How do you get a discount
6	16.10.2024	Anonymous	Every day	of course	very important	fare	20% or higher	10	personal transport	monthly ticket Payariq	Online (via websi	
8	16.10.2024	Anonymous	Every day	of course	very significant	fare	No discount	1	public transport	monthly ticket Samarkand Qoras	Online (via websi	
3	16.10.2024	Anonymous	several times a week	possibly	very significant	security	No discount	9	personal transport	monthly ticket Djizzakh	Online (via websi	
3	16.10.2024	Anonymous	Every day	of course	very important	security	20% or higher	10	public transport	monthly ticket Samarkand region	Online (via websi	
3	16.10.2024	Anonymous	Rarely	possibly	very important	convenienc	20% or higher	10	infantry	annual ticket Tashkent	Online (via websi	
3	16.10.2024	Anonymous	Every day	of course	very significant	convenienc	20% or higher	10	public transport	monthly ticket Samarkand city	Online (via websi	
3	16.10.2024	Anonymous	several times a week	of course	very important	convenienc	20% or higher	10	public transport	monthly ticket Samarkand	Online (via websi	
5	16.10.2024	Anonymous	several times a week	of course	very important	convenient	20% or higher	10	public transport	monthly ticket Karshi	Online (via websi	
7	16.10.2024	Anonymous	Every day	of course	very important	convenienc	20% or higher	10	public transport	monthly ticket Djambay	Online (via websi	
		Anonymous	Every day	of course	very important	convenience	20% or higher	10	personal transport	monthly ticket Sogdiana 10 40		
		Anonymous	Rarely	possibly	very significant	journey time	20% or higher	5	personal transport	annual ticket Tashkent city		
		Anonymous	several times a week	of course	very important	journey time	20% or higher	9	public transport	monthly ticket Samarkand region		
		Anonymous	several times a week	maybe	very important	journey time	20% or higher	10	public transport	monthly ticket Samarkand city		
		Anonymous	Rarely	maybe	very important	journey time	No discount	8	personal transport	monthly ticket Tashkent region		
		Anonymous	Every day	of course	very important	security	20% or higher	10	public transport	annual ticket Samarkand		
		Anonymous	Every day	of course	very important	journey time	20% or higher	10	both	monthly ticket Djizzakh		

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS:

1. Online surveys were conducted with 162 students from the Samarkand branch of Tashkent State University of Economics using Microsoft Forms to assess their opinions on a new 20% discount offer related to public transportation use. Descriptive statistics were calculated regarding the students' daily use of public transportation. A correlation-regression analysis was carried out to determine the relationship between the 20% financial incentive—based on weekly, monthly, and yearly plans—and the increase in public transport usage. Clear data was collected from 162 students, transcribed, and analyzed to identify common opinions, motivations, and preferences regarding increasing public transport usage.

2. The students noted that the financial incentive could make public transport competitive with the costs of using a private car.

3. According to the analysis results on public transport usage, approximately 73% of the students reported using public transportation daily, while 20% stated they use it several times a week.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, based on the issues raised in the article, if small-sized vehicles and taxis that currently operate illegally in Samarkand city and its surrounding areas are brought under the control of the regional or city transport system, it would, firstly, lead to the establishment of more organized and high-quality services while also increasing the income generated from these services. Secondly, it would help control traffic congestion in the city and address environmental issues. Our research also proposes introducing discounted tickets on public transportation. The analysis of the online survey data collected from students at the Samarkand branch of Tashkent State University of Economics revealed that the students' opinions on the convenience and

financial benefits of 20% discount cards for public transport were positive. All suggestions and results were supported by the data presented in the tables and charts included in the article.

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